

Thermodynamics of CoSO₄ and NiSO₄ in Mixed Solvents from Conductance Method

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The ion-solvent interaction of CoSO₄ and NiSO₄ with organic solvent (10, 20 and 30 wt%) glycerol-, glycol- and isopropanol-water mixtures at different temperatures has been studied by conductance method. The dissociation constant has been calculated along with ΔG_i° , ΔG_i° (el) and ΔG° (ch) and the ion-solvent interaction has been inferred.

THE physical properties of the mixed solvents, like glycerol-water, glycol-water and isopropanol-water, viz. dielectric constant, dipole moments are very much different from that of water. These organic solvents are more or less aprotic, whereas water is both an electron donor and an acceptor. These and several other properties make a study of their aqueous mixtures an interesting thing to explore, particularly of the ionic processes accompanying the solution of strong electrolytes.

In the present communication, the conductivities of CoSO₄ and NiSO₄ in glycerol-water, glycol-water and isopropanol-water mixtures at 30 to 45° have been studied at 10, 20 and 30% by weight of the organic solvent to investigate the ion-solvent interaction.

Experimental

The salts CoSO₄ and NiSO₄ used were of E. Merck (extra pure) grade. The purification of glycerol, glycol and isopropanol, preparation of the solvents, solutions and measurement of conductance had been described previously¹. The conductance measurements were within accuracy of ± 0.002 and the concentration range was from 0.02 to 0.002 mol dm⁻³. The temperature of the investigation was from 303 to 318 ± 0.01 K.

Results and Discussion

The Onsager equation² for a completely dissociated electrolytes is

$$\Lambda = \Lambda^\circ - (A + B\Lambda^\circ)\sqrt{I}$$

where, A and B are Onsager constants. It satisfactorily accounts for the change in equivalent conduc-

tivity with concentration. Correct evaluation of Λ° can be made by extrapolating to zero concentration of the plot of Λ vs $c^{1/2}$. However, the above method of extrapolation is unreliable in the cases of a number of electrolytes involving incomplete dissociation or ion-association. In the present case, the dielectric constant of the medium is lowered and there is a great probability of ion-association. Hence, the method of Fuoss and Krauss³ and that of Shedlovsky⁴ have been utilised to calculate the values of Λ° and the dissociation constant. The Λ° and K values calculated by both the methods are in good agreement and are given in Tables 1 and 2. The K values are found to decrease with the increase in temperature for all the solvent compositions and for both the salts. The K values also decrease with the decrease in dielectric constant caused by the increase in organic solvent. This is attributed to the incomplete dissociation or ion-association.

The standard thermodynamic parameters, ΔG_i° have been calculated in the usual manner⁵. The plot of ΔG° vs solvent composition were found to be linear. The extrapolated values gave the thermodynamic parameters for aqueous solutions. The standard thermodynamic quantities (ΔG_i°) for transfer process from water to 10, 20 and 30% of organic solvent-water could be calculated by using Feakins method⁶. The probable uncertainties in ΔG_i° is ± 15 J mol⁻¹. The ΔG_i° values are negative which indicates that the ion-pairs are in a lower energy-state in aquo-organic solvents than in water and hence the ion-pair formation is favoured by decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium.

Single-ion values of free energy are not available presently for the solvent mixture studied. Hence, the method adopted by Khoo and Chan⁷ was followed to study ion-solvent interaction. The Born

TABLE 1— Δ° VALUE ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$)

Temp. °C	Glycerol-water			Glycol-water			Isopropanol-water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CoSO ₄									
30	121.4	100.6	84.3	120.5	108.4	87.5	110.9	81.6	60.2
35	132.8	111.4	92.5	134.8	112.6	95.8	116.2	87.4	63.4
40	143.9	119.5	99.8	143.4	120.4	100.8	121.8	92.4	66.5
45	151.2	127.3	105.2	159.5	129.8	113.4	128.9	100.6	71.4
NiSO ₄									
30	130.4	102.8	83.4	126.5	100.4	86.5	114.2	80.4	62.2
35	138.5	112.4	89.9	136.4	113.5	90.4	118.5	85.2	65.8
40	144.6	114.8	100.4	139.5	119.6	95.4	124.2	89.4	70.4
45	152.6	128.4	113.2	142.6	123.4	99.8	132.2	94.5	75.4

TABLE 2—K VALUE ($\times 10^3$)

Temp. °C	Glycerol-water			Glycol-water			Isopropanol-water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CoSO ₄									
30	6.3	4.2	3.7	6.9	5.1	4.0	7.5	6.2	4.6
35	6.2	4.3	3.8	6.8	5.0	4.0	7.6	6.1	4.5
40	6.1	4.3	3.6	6.8	5.0	3.9	7.4	6.0	4.4
45	6.2	4.1	3.5	6.7	4.9	3.8	7.3	6.1	4.4
NiSO ₄									
30	5.8	4.0	3.4	6.6	4.8	3.7	7.1	5.8	4.2
35	5.7	4.1	3.4	6.5	4.7	3.8	7.0	5.7	4.1
40	5.6	4.0	3.5	6.4	4.6	3.6	7.0	5.6	4.0
45	5.6	3.9	3.4	6.4	4.6	3.5	6.9	5.6	4.0

TABLE 3— ΔG_i° (el) VALUE (J mol^{-1})

Temp. °C	Glycerol-water			Glycol-water			Isopropanol-water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CoSO ₄									
30	250	800	1288	300	520	804	740	1530	2772
35	350	890	1328	300	522	808	760	1545	2794
40	400	890	1334	405	525	810	770	1558	2844
45	450	880	1320	360	575	820	790	1588	2892
NiSO ₄									
30	310	700	1162	272	482	740	50	300	310
35	310	702	1181	272	490	745	100	310	320
40	315	708	1194	300	495	775	102	322	342
45	320	710	1202	310	505	795	120	334	362

TABLE 4— ΔG_i° (sh) VALUE (J mol^{-1})

Temp. °C	Glycerol-water			Glycol-water			Isopropanol-water		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CoSO ₄									
30	-1200	-2670	-3478	-1020	-1940	-2894	-1360	-2700	-5142
35	-1250	-2930	-3488	-1070	-2082	-2938	-1440	-2795	-4924
40	-1350	-2760	-3664	-1185	-2245	-3030	-1480	-2758	-4854
45	-1380	-2900	-3760	-1180	-2225	-3140	-1480	-2718	-4922
NiSO ₄									
30	-1370	-2690	-3671	-1162	-2022	-3030	-700	-1460	-2280
35	-1530	-2762	-3695	-1152	-2200	-3005	-790	-1530	-2380
40	-1595	-2858	-3694	-1230	-2285	-3205	-602	-1602	-2502
45	-1610	-2960	-3812	-1250	-2325	-3225	-860	-1624	-2542

equation was expected to fit increasingly better as the organic solvent content is increased. It was possible to split the ΔG_i° values into two parts as Roy *et al.*⁹ had done, *i.e.*, 'chemical contribution' denoted in their terminology by $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{ch})$ and an electrical contribution, $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{el})$ could be calculated from the Born equation.

From a knowledge of $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{el})$, the chemical contribution of free energy transfer $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{ch})$ could be calculated by subtracting the respective electrostatic contribution values from molar quantities. $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{el})$ and $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{ch})$ values are given in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{ch})$, *i.e.* chemical contribution to the free energy of transfer is negative in all cases and hence the process is thermodynamically favourable as far as the chemical interactions are concerned. Since $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{el})$ is positive (Table 3), the lower the value the greater is the ion-solvent interaction and the order for Co^{II} is glycol-water > glycerol-water > isopropanol-water, whereas for Ni^{II} it is isopropanol-water > glycol-water > glycerol-water.

Glycerol has three OH groups, glycol has two OH whereas isopropanol has only one OH group and water is both an electron donor and acceptor. So the 3-dimensional water structure is broken down in presence of $\text{Ni}^{\text{2+}}$, $\text{Co}^{\text{2+}}$ and $\text{SO}_4^{\text{2-}}$ and the order is dependent on the nature of the ion.

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